

LANGUAGE ATTITUDE OF TEGAL JAVANESE DIALECT MAINTENANCE ON FOOD STALL SELLERS IN DEPOK, INDONESIA

Putri Anggraeni Machmud,

Erni Hastutiⁱ

Faculty of Letters and Culture,
Universitas Gunadarma,
Indonesia

Abstract:

This research aims to find out the language attitudes and language maintenance factors that affect the language use of Tegal Javanese Dialect on food stall sellers in Depok. This research combined the quantitative and qualitative method. The data derived from the distribution of research questionnaires, interviews, observation to food stall sellers in Depok. This research showed the positive of language attitude towards Tegal Javanese Dialect in which they are proud and still use Tegal Javanese Dialect for communication even though they are far from their hometown. There are several language maintenance factors that affect the language use of respondents such age, education level, place of birth and mobility. Their positive language attitudes, so the usage of Tegal Javanese Dialect is still maintained by the food stall sellers.

Keywords: language attitude, language maintenance, Javanese language

1. Introduction

Local languages carry out the usual functions as natural languages used by their speakers. In the local community life, the local language is used by the supporting community in its local scope which is only used in certain geographical environments. In Indonesia there are 742 languages. The majority of local languages in Indonesia have become extinct, some are endangered. Tegal Javanese Dialect is a language with a large number of speakers and the use of Tegal Javanese Dialect is very widespread as a social language in the family and community, for that Tegal Javanese Dialect has its own function as Javanese identity. As stated by Kramsch (1998) that identity is basically the main reason why people tend to keep using their local language. Their purpose is to introduce who they are, as individuals or social groups.

Language maintenance is the state of being still chosen and using mother tongue in their verbal interactions with members of other language groups even though available other languages are mastered or as the decision to continue the collective use of language by a

ⁱ Correspondence: email anggraenipa7@gmail.com; erni@staff.gunadarma.ac.id

community that has used that language before. Chaer (2004) Language maintenance is a matter of attitude or assessment of a language to keep using that language in the midst of other languages. Based on the understanding of language attitudes and language maintenance, Garcia (2003, p.28) stated that language attitude affects language maintenance.

The attitude language can be seen in the form of language use, namely in oral and written communication. In oral form, language communities use language as a means of direct communication with local languages, meanwhile the use of language in written form is written. According to Garvin and Mathiot (1968) Language attitude has three dimensions such as (1) language loyalty that encourages people to maintain their language and if necessary to prevent the influence of other languages; (2) the pride of language that encourages someone to develop language and use it as a symbol of identity; (3) awareness of norms that encourage people to use language based on the context. Someone is required to use the language (formal situation) in accordance with the rules that apply to that language. Attitudes toward language are closely related to language choice. With the attitude of the language possessed, someone chooses what language to use in certain situations. Quoting Fishman (1972) who speaks what language to whom and when. People's attitude toward language can be seen from how they think about language, how they use language, with whom they use, where and how often they use the language. Language attitude studies will determine that people's attitude towards language might be positive or negative.

Research on the language attitude of a particular community is very important because the attitude of community plays a key role in the success of the survival of a language. The research of language attitudes is also carried out due to language contact between one language and another. Language contact results in a language being seen as a more prestigious language. Research on language attitudes towards language maintenance has been carried out (Wilian 2006, Karahan 2007, Huang and Kuo 2015) and the most recent study was conducted by (Adnyana, 2018) regarding language attitudes of people in the Province of Bali towards the Trunyan Balinese Dialect. The research results showed that the attitude of the younger generation of discourses towards the Trunyan Balinese Dialect was positive in which can be analyzed from three aspects of language attitudes namely cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Tegal Javanese Dialect society is a bilingual community, thus the Tegal Javanese Dialect community began to feel anxious about the existence of Javanese. In the globalization era, the use of Tegal Javanese Dialect is no longer monolingual, but they use more than one language or more than one language variation. From the explanation above, this research aims to determine the language attitude and Tegal Javanese Dialect maintenance factors on food stall sellers in Depok.

2. Methods

This research combines quantitative and qualitative approaches to see the tendency of language choice used and explain the facts that actually occur in the field. The research was conducted in Depok, West Java, which is a direct border with DKI Jakarta and Depok is as one of the urban destinations. Depok residents come from various ethnic groups with different

mother tongue backgrounds. Among the population of Depok City which is dominated by Betawi language communities, there are groups of migrants who are speakers of Javanese, Minang, Batak and Sundanese languages. The data analyzed are information obtained from questionnaires, interviews, and observations regarding the use and attitude of the Tegal Javanese Dialect community in Depok, West Java.

The information was excavated from several sources, namely: 1) Informants of married men and women of food stall sellers, ranging from elementary school age up to 60 years and over with different social backgrounds; 2) Communication events in various domains, such as family, work, education, religion, neighborhood, transactions, and outside the home domain. In this research, data collection was carried out in several ways, namely: 1) Questionnaire, which is in the form of a list of questions arranged in accordance with the objectives of the study. Compile a list of questions that contain respondents' language choices by formulating the question of who talks to whom, what the topic is, and in what situations; 2) Interview which aims to explore information related to research problems; 3) Observations made with involved recording conversations, diaries, 4) Document search by searching documents to obtain data about the geographical and demographic or socio-cultural conditions of the people in Depok. A total of 30 respondents were recorded based on gender, age, marital status, education, occupation, and place of birth. Then tabulate data, namely by entering data into tables in various categories. The last stage, namely the calculation of percentages based on the number of answers entered. The variables examined in this research consisted of independent and dependent variables. Respondent data is an independent variable, while the use and choice of language and language attitude are the dependent variables that determine the maintenance level. Data processing is done by first categorizing the data derived from survey questionnaires, interviews, and observations involved.

3. Results and Discussion

The attitude of the Tegal Javanese dialect maintenance can be related to the sociolinguistic background of the speech community including demographics, and population mobility. Internally the emphasis is on the domain of Tegal Javanese dialect usage. Based on the findings and discussion, in general the description of Tegal Javanese dialect maintenance is presented as follows:

Table 1: Language Attitude of the Respondents towards Tegal Javanese Dialect Mastery

Respondent	Very important		Important		Not important		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Husband	7	58,3	5	41,7	-	0	12	100
Wife	10	55,6	7	38,8	1	5,6	18	100

According to the table above, the language attitude of the respondents towards mastering the Tegal Javanese dialect mostly answered "very important". Husband respondent answers: 7 people (58.3%) answered "very important", 5 people (41.7%) answered "important" and the answer "not important" was blank. In addition, wife respondents, 10 people (55.6%) answered

"very important", 7 people (38.8%) answered "important" and 1 person (5.6%) answered "not important". Almost all respondents said that Tegal Javanese dialect was very important because Tegal Javanese dialect is their native language and part of their culture, they did not want Tegal Javanese dialect to become extinct.

Table 2: Language Attitudes of Respondents towards their Children's Desire to Speak Tegal Javanese Dialect

Respondent	Yes		No		Do not know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Husband	12	100	-	0	-	0	12	100
Wife	16	88,9	2	11,1	-	0	18	100

Based on table, the respondent's language attitude about his children's desire to speak Tegal Javanese dialect from the respondent's husband's answers as many as 12 people (100%) answered "yes". There were 16 wife respondents (88.9%) answered "yes", and 2 others (11.1%) answered "no". The reason the husband and wife respondents answered "yes" was wanting their children to be able to preserve their own local language so that they would not become extinct and be able to communicate with their extended families when they returned to their hometown.

Table 3: The Language Use Situation of Tegal Javanese Dialect in Food Stall

Respondents	Tegal Javanese Dialect		Indonesian		Mix Language		Jumlah	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
<= 50 years old	12	46	6	23	8	31	26	100
> 50 years old	2	50	1	25	1	25	4	100

Table 4: The Language Use Situation of Tegal Javanese Dialect outside Food Stall

Respondents	Tegal Javanese Dialect		Indonesian		Mix Language		Jumlah	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
<= 50 years old	15	58	4	15	7	27	26	100
> 50 years old	3	75	1	25	-	0	4	100

Furthermore, the authors discuss the use of language based on age with the situation in the Food stall and outside the Food stall. Respondents consisted of husband and wife respondents who were divided into two age groups, there are age less than 50 years, 50 years and age more than 50 years. From the data obtained, 46% of respondents aged less than 50 years used Tegal Javanese Dialect, 31% used mixed languages and 23% used Indonesian. The data is based on the situation in Food stall. While the situation outside Food stall, there are 58% who use Tegal Javanese Dialect, 27% use mixed languages, and another 15% use Indonesian. Whereas 50% of respondents aged over 50 years with the situation in the Food stall claimed to use Tegal Javanese Dialect, 25% used Indonesian and another 25% used Mix language. Whereas for situations outside the Food stall there are 75% of respondents who use Tegal Javanese Dialect, and another 25% use Indonesian. From these data it can be concluded that all the respondents still maintain Javanese language. It can be seen that age does not affect the use of language in

respondents both in the Food stall and outside the Food stall. All the age groups are dominant use Javanese when in the Food stall and outside the Food stall

Table 5: Language Use Based on Education Level
 (the situation in food stalls)

Respondents	Javanese Tegal Dialect		Indonesian		Mix Language		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Elementary school	10	58,8	1	5,8	6	35,3	17	100
High school	7	58,3	3	25	2	16,7	12	100
College	-	0	1	100	-	0	1	100

Table 6: Language Use Based on Level of Education
 (the situation outside food stalls)

Respondent	Javanese		Indonesian		Mix Language		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Elementary school	11	64,7	2	11,7	4	23,5	17	100
High school	5	41,7	3	25	4	33,3	12	100
College	-	0	1	100	-	0	1	100

Furthermore, on the table above described the language use based on the level of education. Respondents consisted of three education level groups, there are elementary school, high school and college. Based on research that has been done, if they are in food stall, the three groups of respondents use more Indonesian to communicate. The situation was outside food stall, respondents with elementary school education level mostly used Javanese with a percentage of 64.7%. Respondents with high school education level also mostly use Javanese with a percentage of 41.7% and respondents with college education level use Indonesian to communicate with a percentage of 100%. With these data, it can be concluded that if the level of education is high, the use of the Javanese language is getting lower, because respondents who have a high level of education are accustomed to using Indonesian because they always use Indonesian to communicate at school.

Table 7: Language Use Based on Place of Birth
 (the situation in food stalls)

Place of Birth	Javanese Tegal Dialect		Indonesian		Mix Language		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Tegal	10	43,5	8	34,8	5	21,7	23	100
Outside Tegal	2	28,6	1	14,3	4	57,1	7	100

Table 8: Language Use Based on Place of Birth
 (the situation outside food stalls)

Place of Birth	Javanese Tegal Dialect		Indonesian		Mix Language		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Tegal	15	65,2	3	13	5	21,7	23	100
Outside Tegal	2	28,6	1	14,3	4	57,1	7	100

Furthermore, the use of language based on the birth place of respondent which consisted of husband and wife with situations in and outside food stall. The respondent's place of birth consists of Java and outside Java. Based on the existing table, the language used by 10 respondents (43.5%) who was born in Java when the situation in the food stall claimed to use Indonesian, 8 people (34.8%) used Javanese and 5 people (21.7%) uses mixed languages. While there are 4 respondents (57.1%) who were born outside Java using Indonesian, 2 people (28.6%) use Javanese and there are 1 person (14.3%) using mixed languages such Indonesian and Javanese. Whereas, the situation outside food stall, 15 respondents (65.2%) who were born in Java claimed to use Javanese, 5 people (21.7%) used mixed languages and 3 respondents (13%) used Indonesian. In addition, 3 respondents (42.8%) born outside Java used Javanese, 3 respondents (42.8%) used Indonesian and 1 person (14.3%) used mixed language. Based on these data, it can be concluded that respondents born in Java use more Javanese than respondents born outside Java.

4. Language use in Mobility

The length of stay in Depok, there are 30 respondent which divided into 8 respondents who claimed to have lived in Depok for less than 5 years, 8 others claimed to have lived in Depok 5 to 10 years and 14 others had lived in Depok for more than 10 years. Based on the observation, even though the respondent has become a resident of Depok, if there is a respondent's family who is sick or dies in their hometown, they immediately return home, and for once a year the respondent usually returns home to celebrate Eid al-Fitr as well as tightening the kinship with the family.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the questionnaire and interview language attitudes affect the level of Javanese language maintenance shows that their language attitude is positive towards Javanese and the use of Javanese is still maintained by their community, because they do not want their language to go extinct and their children do not know about their language and culture. Parent and adult age respondents have positive language attitudes with a strong level of language maintenance. However, in young respondents, it was found that a positive language attitude did not mean that the language maintenance rate was also strong. There are the Javanese language maintenance factors that affect the Javanese language maintenance of respondents such as age, education level, place of birth and mobility.

References

- Adnyana, I. Ketut. Suar (2018). Sikap Bahasa Guyub T tutur Bahasa Bali Dialek trunyan. *Jurnal Tutur*. Vol 4. No. 1. ISSN 2442-3475.
- Chaer, A., & Agustina, L. (2004). *Sosiolinguistik Perkenalan Awal*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta

- Fishman, J. A. (1972). *Readings in the Sociology of Language*. Giglio: Mouton & C.o.
- Hung, D. L. J. and Kuo, M., Y. M. (2015). A Case Study of Language Attitude: How Do Taiwanese Females View Mandarin-Speaking and Taiwanese-Speaking Males?. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*. Vol. 4(2).
- Karahan. F. (2007). Language attitudes of Turkish students towards the English language and its use in Turkish context. *Journal of Arts and Sciences*. Vol. 1. Issue 7.
- Kramsch (1998). *Language and Culture*. London: Cambridge University Press.
- Garcia, M. (2003). Recent research in language maintenance. *Annual review of Applied linguistics*, pp.22-43. USA: Cambridge University Press.
- Garvin, Paul and M. Mathiot (1968). *The Urbanization of Guarani Language: Problem in Language and Culture* in J.A. Fishman (ed) 1972. *Reading in Sociology of Language*, Giglio: Mouton & C.o.
- Wilian, Sudirman (2006). *Pemertahanan Bahasa dan Pergeseran Identitas Etnis. Kajian Atas Dwibahasawan Sumbawa-Sasak Lombok*. Dissertation. Depok: Universitas Indonesia.

Putri Anggraeni Machmud, Erni Hastuti
LANGUAGE ATTITUDE OF TEGAL JAVANESE DIALECT MAINTENANCE
ON FOOD STALL SELLERS IN DEPOK, INDONESIA

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). and European Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).